

A Study on Affecting the Struggle of Women Entrepreneurs in India

¹Mrs. Anitha .A & ²Dr. R.Sritharan

¹Research Scholar, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore (India)

²Assit. Prof. of. Business Administration in Annamalai University, Chidambaram (India)

ARTICLE DETAILS

Article History

Published Online: 09 Mar 2019

Keywords

Women Entrepreneurship, nature of the business, Factor Affecting Women Entrepreneurs, Problems of Women Entrepreneurs

ABSTRACT

In Indian women entrepreneurs lot of problems faced in society not only for the individual but also for the business. The company creation process entails many actions and roles which the women Entrepreneurs have to complete while facing high risk, uncertainty, and high responsibility and financial insecurity. This can be a difficult experience for women entrepreneurs and can result in physical and mental strain such burnout, where the latter is characterized by tiredness, and little work efficacy.

This study is to analyze the factor affecting the struggle of women entrepreneurs in India. A sample of 100 women entrepreneurs was surveyed by using the questionnaire. The results of the investigations by using descriptive statics method and identified the factors of the problems affecting by women entrepreneurs. These factors were classified into four categories of i) Entrepreneurial problems, ii) Social and personal problems, iii) Technical problems, iv) Marketing problems by women entrepreneurs. The research showing a percentage of factors affecting the struggle of women entrepreneurs based on the opinions of respondents.

1. Introduction

Women Entrepreneurs goings-on the ability to create innovations and competitiveness, leading the way for new business and job creation; which is crucial for many economies. In addition to economic benefits, ecological sustainability is an increasing concern and is viewed as an inclusive approach to economic health, social equity and environmental resilience. Women Entrepreneurs are assumed to be an important driving force of this sustainable big business trend as they push environmental conscious innovations that have the ability to disrupt the market and existing industrial standards whereby reducing the overall negative environmental impact of human.

2. Concept of women entrepreneurs

Women Entrepreneurs may be defined as the women or a group of women who initiate, organize and operate a business enterprise. The Government of India has defined women entrepreneurs as —an enterprise owned and controlled by women having a minimum financial interest of 51 per cent of the capital and giving at least 51 per cent of the employment generated in the enterprise to women. Women entrepreneurs engaged in business due to push and pull factors which encourage women to have an independent occupation and stands on their on legs.

3. Problems of women entrepreneurs

Women Entrepreneurs encounter two sets of problems i.e. general problems and specific problems to women entrepreneurs. These are discussed follows.

General Problems:

- Problem of Finance

- Scarcity of Raw Materials
- Male dominated Society.
- Lack of Education
- Market Oriented Risk
- Motivational Factors.
- Lack of Confidence
- Training Programs

Specific Problems:

- Entrepreneurial problems,
- Social and personal problems,
- Technical problems,
- Marketing problems

4. Research Methodology

This study was contact to affecting struggle of the women entrepreneurs. The Survey method was used to collect data and structured questionnaire was used as a tool to determine views of respondents. A sample of 100 respondents from collected in Indian women entrepreneurs.

Data Collection

- ✓ Primary data
- ✓ Secondary data

5. Objectives

1. To find the opinion of the respondents and compare the nature of the business by the women entrepreneurs.
2. To analyse factors affecting the problems of women entrepreneurs.

6. Analysis and discussion

Table-1 Demographic Profile Analysis
The opinion of the respondents and compare the nature of the business by the women entrepreneurs

Particulars	Nature of business		
	Food production	Handicrafts	Textiles
Age			
Below30 Years	10	43	47
31 – 40 Years	45	33	22
41 and older	45	24	31
Total	100	100	100
Education			
Post-Graduate	29	29	42
Graduate	43	33	51
Higher Secondary	21	23	4
Below higher secondary	7	15	3
Total	100	100	100
Marital Status			
Married	42	46	12
Unmarried	34	42	24
Divorced	24	12	64
Total	100	100	100

Table 1 show that 47% of the respondents textiles business the age group of below 30 years, compared to marital status the married women entrepreneurs only 12% doing the textiles business and 42% o the respondents Post-Graduate , 22% of the respondents textiles business the age group of 30-40 years, compared to marital status the unmarried women entrepreneurs only 24% doing the textiles business and 51% of the respondents Graduate, 31% of the respondents textiles business the age group of 41 and older, compared to marital status Divorced women entrepreneurs 64% doing the textiles business and , Higher Secondary 04%,below higher secondary only 03%,

43% of the respondents handicrafts business the age group of below 30 years, compared to marital status the married women entrepreneurs 46% doing the handicrafts business and 29% o the respondents Post-Graduate , 33% of the respondents handicrafts the age group of 30-40 years, compared to marital status the unmarried women entrepreneurs only 42% doing the handicrafts and 33% of the respondents Graduate, 24% of the respondents handicrafts the age group of 41 and older, compared to marital status Divorced women entrepreneurs 12% doing the handicrafts , Higher Secondary 23%,and below higher secondary 15%,

10% of the respondents Food productions business the age group of below 30 years, compared to marital status the married women entrepreneurs 42% doing the Food productions business and 29% o the respondents Post-Graduate , 45% of the respondents Food productions the age group of 30-40 years, compared to marital status the unmarried women entrepreneurs only 34% doing the Food productions and 43% of the respondents Graduate, 45% of the respondents Food productions the age group of 41 and older, compared to marital status Divorced women

entrepreneurs 24% doing the Food productions and , Higher Secondary 21%, below higher secondary 07%,

It conclude most of the women entrepreneurs doing food productions business.

Table 2: Factors Affecting Women Entrepreneurs

The factors the problems affecting by women entrepreneurs using the percentage method

Factors affecting women entrepreneurs	Number of respondents	Percentage
Entrepreneurial problems	48	48%
Social and personal problems	16	19%
Technical problems	17	16%
Marketing problems	19	17%
Total	100	100

Show the Tables 2 detailed the factors of the problems affecting by women entrepreneurs. These factors were classified into four categories of i) Entrepreneurial problems, ii) Social and personal problems, iii) Technical problems, iv) Marketing problems. According to the views of respondents, the entrepreneurial problems are highest affecting in other categories. 48% of the women entrepreneurs are of the view that category, Marketing is the second most affecting category, while the Social and personal problems, Technical problems are ranked third and fourth according to the statistics of 16%, 17% and 19% respectively.

7. Suggestions to improve women entrepreneurship

- To give Training in vocational and business skills could empower women entrepreneurs
- To give totally Focus on personal empowerment skills

- original participatory approaches to education, information and problem solving rather than conventional methods
- Creating a good climate for female entrepreneurs by initiate macroeconomic policies
- Special financial support schemes that help them in raising capital.

8. Conclusion

Pressure in the work place is a commonality throughout world in every business. Managing that struggle becomes vital

in order to keep up job performance as well as relationship with co-workers and individual life. Changing the work environment relieves that the problems. Making the environment less competitive between employees decreases some amounts of the problems. The study was conducted at the Indian women entrepreneurs to collect relevant information. After studying the result we obtained, that due to the dual role that women perform which are household work and her profession they have the signs of the problems but it can be managed by proper planning.

Reference

1. Ahmad S. and Xavier S. (2010) Stress and coping styles of entrepreneurs: A Malaysian survey, *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 14(1), pp. 25–36.
2. Ahl, H., (2006). 'Why research on women entrepreneurs needs new directions', *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, Vol. 30, No. 5, August, pp. 596-621
3. Anderson C. (1992) The relationship between locus of control, decision behaviours, and performance in a stress setting: a longitudinal study, *Academy of Management Proceedings*, 1(1), pp. 65–69.
4. Chhichhia V. (2004) Problems faced by Women Entrepreneurs and Importance of Training in their Entrepreneurs, in National seminar on Women Entrepreneurship. Vadodara, India: Development of Home Science Extension and Communication.
5. Das M. (2000) Women Entrepreneurs from India: Problems, Motivations and Success Factors, *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 15(4), pp. 67–81.
6. Iyer M. R. (2016) A Study On Problems Faced By Women Entrepreneurs In Ernakulam District, Kerala, *International Journal of Development Research*, 6(7), pp. 8616–8620.
7. Jai parkash and meenu goyal (2011). Women entrepreneurship in india-problems and prospects zenith international journal of multidisciplinary research vol.1 (5)
8. Jahanshahi, A. A., Pitamber, B. K., & Nawaser, K. (2010). Issues and challenges for women entrepreneurs in global scene, with special reference to India. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 4(9), 4347–4356.
9. Kapadia S. and Barodia S. (2004) 'Women Entrepreneurs: Problems and Difficulties', in National seminar on Women Entrepreneurship.
10. Kumar D. (2006) Problems of Women Entrepreneurs in India, *Indian MBA*.
11. Mathew, R. V., & Panchanatham, N. (2011). An Exploratory Study on the Work-Life Balance of Women Entrepreneurs in South India. *Asian Academy of Management Journal*, 16(2), 77–105.